

“Easy French” Subtitle Conventions

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French Transcript Line

Symbols

CONVENTION	DESCRIPTION	REPRESENTATION
(word)	Parentheses	Transcriber’s best interpretation of unclear or unintelligible speech into standard orthography; Recasting of clear mistakes (<i>le</i> instead of <i>la</i> , etc.)
[implicit words]	Square brackets	Implied word or information; Word added for clarity
...	Three separate periods (not one auto-replace character)	Clear pause; Ellipsis
(...)	Three periods between parentheses	Unclear or unintelligible speech
clipped-	Hyphen at end of a word	Halting or abrupt cut off of sound or word
turn - taking	Space-hyphen-space *No period before hyphen, but include question marks and exclamation points <i>C’est bien - Oui, c’est bien.</i> <i>Tu aimes ça? - Oui.</i> <i>Tu aimes ça! - Oui.</i>	Participant turn-taking in a single subtitle
"reported"	Quotation marks Examples regarding punctuation : "Meuf" veut dire quoi? Il a dit "je veux pas". Il a dit "oui" et elle a dit "non". Il a dit "Oui!" Il a demandé "Puis-je partir?"	Reported speech; Metalinguistic discussion

Conventions for interjections, verbal tickets, speech gestures etc.

CONVENTION	ENGLISH	DESCRIPTION
Ah	Ah	Interjection marking a cheerful surprise or admiration
Euh	Uh, um, er	Hesitation
Heu, hum	Hmm	Self-interrogation or questioning, pondering
Ben	Uh, er, well	Marking surprise or hesitation
		*No marks for laughing or related non-linguistic sounds that can be heard from the video
Enfin, ‘fin		Hedging marker sometimes similar to “I mean” Slight preference for the full form, but can be written <i>fin</i> if need be or preferred
Mhh (mhh)	Uh-huh	Informal mark of “yes” or “yeah”

Orthographic Conventions

I write out full forms when possible except in the following cases:

- I do not write *ne* in *ne...pas* when it is not pronounced
- I do orthographic *élision* between pronouns and following words if they start with a vowel (for example, *Tu as dit* → *T’as dit*) but not with a consonant (*Je suis* or *je sais pas* and NOT *j’suis* and *j’sais pas*)

For loanwords or nonce borrowings I occasionally preserve their English or other language orthography.

English/French Translation Lines

My translations are “free translation;” nonetheless, I aim for more literal translations in English when possible.

Symbols

CONVENTION	DESCRIPTION	REPRESENTATION
(word)		Implicit word added to the translation
turn - taking	Space-hyphen-space	Participant turn-taking in a single subtitle
clipped-	Hyphen at end of a word	Clipped speech; Halting, abrupt cut off of sound or word.
[additional]	Square brackets Belleville [a neighborhood in Paris]	Additional information or a comment from the transcriber
(...)		Unclear or unintelligible speech
"reported"		Reported speech;

		metalinguistic discussion; Untranslated French word
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Shortening Conventions

To enable each tier of a subtitle image to fit onto a single line, I often use:

In English, expressions such as *gonna*, *gotta*, etc.

General

For reasons of space, I sometimes omit non-essential elements that I would normally have preferred for a free translation.